

MECHANISMS OF DEVELOPMENT OF AXIOLOGICAL COMPETENCES IN STUDENTS

¹Ibraimov Xolboy Ibragimovich, ²Siddikov Bakhtiyor Saidkulovich

¹Director of the Scientific Research Institute of Pedagogical Sciences of Uzbekistan named after T.N.Kori Niyozzi. Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor.

²Associated professor, candidate of pedagogical sciences, Ferghana state university

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Abstract. *In this article, it was determined that in the development of axiological competencies of students, their spiritual values, social orientation, ideals, and life strategies are important. Also, the mechanisms and stages of developing axiological competencies in students are discussed in detail.*

Keywords: *students, axiological, axiological competence, infrastructure, mechanisms.*

In the world, in recent years, the problem of studying the inner potential of a person, aimed at increasing the value of a person, has become one of the priority areas of pedagogy, and the main components of educational mechanisms: personal health, organization of one's own activities, self-development, o Concepts such as self-determination in the community and self-realization in the infrastructures of society indicate that the individual is in the position of universal values. As the understanding of the nature of events, processes, and events that are valuable for a person occurs in the process of axiology, the problems of developing axiological value system in young people in social infrastructures, educating them as specialists with high morals, humanitarian qualities, and deep knowledge of their profession issues of scientific and pedagogical research are in the lead.

Raising the level of axiological competences, forming loyalty to national and universal values among students studying in general secondary educational institutions was carried out on the basis of the principle of relying on the achieved positive results and achievements.

Formation and development of axiological competences of young people in social infrastructures, development of spiritual and moral qualities in them is carried out on the basis of the principle of accuracy and speed.

According to the analysis of the literature, the researchers (F.N.Alkarova, F.Zaripov) proposed a pedagogical process model aimed at organizing situations for the activation of students' practical skills during the period of finding a solution to the research problem.

S.M.Mordanova, a scientist from Kazakhstan, who conducted research on the formation of moral qualities, described the pedagogical model of the formation of moral qualities into moral-oriented, moral-forming, and moral-resulting parts. According to the scientist:

1) the point aimed at ethics - reveals the aspects of formation of moral qualities and draws attention to the formation of moral qualities in students with the help of ethno-pedagogical tools.

2) the moral-forming part of the model is carried out in two directions: a) educational activities with an emphasis on studying the materials of general education subjects for the humanitarian complex b) extracurricular activities, not only regional, regional and republican activities of students is carried out by participating in the events held on the scale.

3) moral result-giving point - it makes it possible to eliminate identified shortcomings and assess the level of formation of moral qualities in students" [3, 77].

R.K.Akchulpanova, in her scientific research work, paid attention to the pedagogical conditions in the spiritual and moral education of students and considers that "spiritual and moral education of students depends on the effective formation of the process of pedagogical conditions. In general, this "pedagogical environment is the implementation of all components of the educational process, from setting the goal to the result through the organization of motives and stimuli, to the activity and its regulation, to the implementation and development of its content. focuses on the "process" [2, 71].

According to F.Zaripov, "in the process of education, the issue of satisfying and educating the will, the positive aspects of a person's character, the formation of positive aspirations, and the aesthetic needs of a person is solved. Therefore, the formation of moral values in students, not only in words, but also in practice, becomes a top priority. Also, Y.F.Zaripov notes that there is a trend that must be taken into account in the organization of the educational process in modern educational institutions:

firstly, the obsolescence of the educational process, the need to culturally re-understand the goals and values of the educational system, which reveals the differentiated nature of the pedagogical influence on the personal development of students;

secondly, taking into account the principle of the social and cultural integrity of a person, it is necessary to further scientifically justify the way of organizing the education of students and integrating its contents into the social and cultural context, with the priority of the idea of spiritual and moral education. given [1, 12].

Based on the mentioned tasks, for use in our research work, it was determined that it is necessary to strengthen the need for participation in spiritual and educational activities in the minds of young students, and to introduce activities that have a positive effect on the development of axiological competencies in them.

It was found that their spiritual values, social orientation, ideals, and life strategies play an important role in the development of axiological competencies in students (Fig. 1).

In this mentioned mechanism, spiritual and moral values, cultural traditions; understanding and respecting universal human values and following the values of society; to remain faithful to the continuing traditions; focusing on honesty and humility as the basis of activity. All of the listed values can serve as criteria for assessing the level of students' axiological competencies.

Analyzing the modern requirements for the development of axiological competencies of students, the mechanism of implementation, we came to the conclusion that it is necessary to make some changes to the concept of developing spiritual and moral qualities.

If the moral nutrition of the student is higher than or equal to the minimum moral standard in the society, then the spiritual and moral nutrition obtained from such activity can be effectively calculated. If the spiritual and moral nutrition received by the student is less than the minimum moral standard, then the spiritual and moral nutrition received from such an activity can be evaluated as ineffective, because it cannot satisfy the spiritual and moral needs of the student. .

In this case, the task of pedagogy is to ensure the effective aspects of the development of axiological competences of students and to identify the ineffective aspects and cover the measures to change it to the effective side.

The improvement of the mechanisms of educational work during the implementation of experimental work in 2020-2023 has created the need to adequately cover the psychological features of education within the framework of these directions.

Figure 1. Mechanism of development of axiological competencies in students

It is an urgent task to carry out large-scale work on increasing the spiritual and moral content of the educational system, developing axiological competences in young people, instilling the spirit of loyalty to national traditions, immunity to foreign ideas and ideologies, and strengthening critical thinking. remains.

In order to expand students' outlook, learn educational information, and develop competences related to the field, it is appropriate to form axiological competencies expressed by students based on certain pedagogical and conceptual approaches. These stages are implemented on the basis of pedagogical conditions, didactic principles, and approaches in the development of axiological competencies of students (see Table 1).

As shown in the table, the stages of development of axiological competencies in students and pedagogical-conceptual approaches ensure the development of their spiritual and moral qualities, express the needs of individual and community development. Their individual development and full self-expression, responsibility, responsibility, team work, mutual support and other valuable qualities bring to adulthood. These goals imply an optimal combination of collective, group and individual forms of organizing the pedagogical process.

The stages of development of axiological competences in students take into account the connections and interdependencies between its main components, that is, the teaching, training and development processes as a component of the integral pedagogical process. is manifested in the interrelationship.

In this case, the connections between student activity and pedagogical relations and the results of its development; the relationship between students' abilities (age, individual) and the nature of pedagogical influences on them; the relationship between students' potential and personality is taken into account in the pedagogical system.

Stages of development of axiological competencies in students

Steps	Pedagogical conditions	Principles of education	Approaches
Evaluation of own activity	Modernization of material and technical base	It is based on the principle of historicity, consciousness	Pedagogical-conceptual
Society, prioritizing the interests of others, management efficiency	Provision of educational, educational-methodical literature	humanity, integrity, consciousness	Competency, systematic
The connection of education with future specialization	Systematization of pedagogical and didactic processes	Connection between theory and practice	Person-oriented
Analytical-synthetic activity	availability of scientific laboratories, classrooms, classrooms, study halls, libraries, as well as the quality of services of information and resource centers	Science	Pragmatic, active
Refleksion	use of modern elements of educational tools	Consistency, sequence	sociogeneti, humanistic, biogenetic

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